

Relationship between librarians' information retrieval skills, digital archiving skills and management of information resources in University libraries in North Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This study investigated the relationship between librarians' information retrieval skills, digital archiving skills, and the management of information resources in university libraries across North Central Nigeria.

Method: Using a correlational survey research design, the study addressed two research questions and tested two null hypotheses. The population comprised all 254 professional librarians in six Federal Universities within the region, with a census sampling approach adopted. Data were gathered through three validated instruments—the Questionnaire on Information Retrieval Skills (QIRS), Questionnaire on Digital Archiving Skills (QDAS), and Management of Information Resources Questionnaire (MIRQ)—all based on a 4-point Likert scale, with Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients of 0.78, 0.81, and 0.71 respectively. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the research questions, while linear regression analysis tested the null hypotheses at 0.05 significance level.

Findings/Results: Pearson correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.88$) between information retrieval skills and information resources management, and a moderate positive relationship ($r = 0.59$) between digital archiving skills and resource management. Linear regression analysis showed that information retrieval skills accounted for 15% of the variance in resource management ($R^2 = 0.150$; $\beta = 0.387$; $p < 0.001$), while digital archiving skills explained a higher 34.5% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.345$; $\beta = 0.588$; $p < 0.001$).

Implications: These findings indicate the significance of information retrieval skills and digital archiving skill in enhancing the effective management of information resources.

Conclusion

The study concludes that information retrieval and digital archiving skills are essential to the successful management of information resources in university libraries.

Recommendations

The study recommends that university libraries in North Central Nigeria invest in continuous professional development programmes to enhance librarians' information retrieval and digital archiving competencies.

Keywords: Digital Archiving Skills, Information Resources, Information Retrieval Skills, Management, University Libraries

Introduction

Information resources are crucial for universities to achieve academic goals. They support research by providing necessary data and knowledge. Chen and Chang (2015) explained that information resources facilitate teaching and learning by offering a variety of resources for lecturers and students. They promote innovation by providing access to up-to-date information, fostering creativity within the academic community. Information resources in university libraries include; Electronic Books (eBooks): These are digital versions of traditional print books, often accessible through online databases; Online Journals: Subscriptions to journals that allow electronic access to articles and publications; Databases: Aggregated collections of academic journals, reports, and various types of research data that can be used for in-depth study; and Institutional Repositories: Digital collections that showcase the scholarly output of the university, including theses, research papers, and presentations (Yebowaah & Owusu-Ansah, 2020). Therefore, management of information resources encompasses a range of activities aimed at ensuring that library resources remain accessible, relevant, and user-friendly.

Managing information resources such as online databases, e-books, and digital journals is crucial for ensuring that users have access to a wide range of academic materials. Therefore, the management of information resources involves the processes and strategies used to acquire, organize, preserve, and provide access to information materials in libraries (Hamad, Al-Fadel and Fakhouri, 2020), effective management ensures that information resources remain relevant, accessible, and useful to users while maintaining their integrity over time. Ovie and Emumekpor (2023) stressed that key aspects of managing information resources include: (i) Acquisition: selecting and

procuring resources that align with the institution's objectives and user needs; (ii) Cataloging and Classification: Organizing resources systematically to facilitate easy retrieval; (iii) Digitization: Converting physical materials into digital formats to enhance accessibility and preservation; (iv) User Services: Providing guidance and support to users in accessing and utilizing resources; (v) Preservation and Conservation: Protecting resources from physical deterioration and obsolescence.

The management of information resources in university libraries, particularly in North Central Nigeria, is undergoing significant transformation. With the rapid advancement of technology and the increasing availability of digital tools, libraries are shifting from traditional print-based systems to hybrid models that integrate both physical and digital resources. However, this shift is not without its challenges. Ango and Akporhonor (2024) stressed that while many university libraries in North Central Nigeria have adopted digital platforms such as online public access catalogs (OPACs) and institutional repositories, the pace of technological integration varies widely. Some libraries remain underfunded and lack the infrastructure needed to fully digitize their collections (Reddy et al., 2020). The digital era demands librarians who are proficient in using and managing digital tools. However, research indicates that not all librarians possess the necessary technical skills or confidence to effectively manage digital resources. This gap in digital proficiency often hinders the efficient management and dissemination of information resources.

Despite facing numerous challenges, university libraries in North Central Nigeria have made significant strides in adopting best practices for the management of information resources. These challenges, which include limited funding, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of trained personnel, have not deterred these libraries from pursuing innovative solutions to enhance their services. One notable area of progress is the establishment of collaborative initiatives, such as library consortia, which have facilitated resource sharing among institutions. These consortia have not only expanded access to scholarly materials but have also reduced costs and improved the overall efficiency of library operations. Additionally, the integration of digital technologies has enabled libraries to transition from traditional, print-based systems to more dynamic, hybrid models that cater to the evolving needs of their users. This shift has been instrumental in bridging the gap between limited physical collections and the growing demand for diverse, up-to-date academic resources.

The successful adoption of these best practices, however, hinges on the ability of librarians to master information retrieval skills, which are essential for navigating both traditional and digital information landscapes. Information retrieval skills encompass a range of competencies, including the ability to efficiently locate, access, and retrieve

information using advanced search techniques, digital platforms, and an understanding of metadata and indexing systems (Thompson (2019). In the context of university libraries, these skills are particularly critical, as they enable librarians to support academic research by guiding users through complex databases and digital repositories (Madukoma, Unegbu & Olorunkalu, 2023). Moreover, as libraries in North Central Nigeria continue to embrace digital transformation, the role of librarians in teaching users how to effectively utilize these resources has become increasingly important. By equipping both themselves and their users with robust information retrieval skills, librarians are not only enhancing the accessibility of scholarly materials but also fostering a culture of self-reliance and critical engagement with information. This, in turn, strengthens the link between the libraries' adoption of best practices and their ability to meet the academic and research needs of their communities.

Digital archiving skills involve the ability to preserve, organize, and provide long-term access to digital resources. This is critical for ensuring that valuable scholarly materials remain accessible despite technological advancements and potential data loss (Giesler, 2019). It requires a combination of technical and organizational skills, including knowledge of digital preservation standards, proficiency in archiving software and tools, and understanding of file formats, metadata standards, and checksum validation for data integrity (Lavoie and Dempsey, 2020). The need for this study stems from the growing demand for efficient management of information resources in academic libraries, which are increasingly required to provide access to both traditional and digital collections.

Empirical evidence underscores the importance of these skills in enhancing library services. For instance, Khan and Bhatti (2017) emphasized that information retrieval skills, including the use of advanced search techniques and understanding metadata, are essential for navigating digital platforms and improving access to scholarly materials. Similarly, digital archiving skills are critical for preserving and organizing digital collections, ensuring their long-term accessibility and usability (Yebowaah & Onwusu-Ansah, 2020). Studies have also shown that libraries with well-trained staff in these areas are better equipped to manage hybrid collections and support academic research (Mamza, Bantai & Aliyu, 2024). However, there is a noticeable gap in the literature regarding the specific impact of these skills on resource management in university libraries in North Central Nigeria. This study seeks to fill this gap by providing empirical insights into how librarians' competencies in information retrieval and digital archiving influence the effective management of information resources, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on library science and digital transformation.

The relationship between librarians' information retrieval skills and the management of information resources in university libraries has gained increasing attention in scholarly research. A study by Ekenna and Mabawonku (2013) revealed a significant correlation between these skills and the effective use of electronic resources, highlighting that students with higher retrieval skills utilized e-resources more efficiently. The study recommended integrating information retrieval training into university curricula to enhance students' research capabilities.

Information retrieval skills enable librarians to efficiently organize and manage academic content within the university library system. In a related study, Adekannbi (2016) found that cognitive skills significantly predicted retrieval abilities, while gender also played a role in informational and operational retrieval skills. The findings suggest that enhancing cognitive skills could improve information retrieval, leading to better management of information resources. The author recommended embedding information retrieval training programs within university curricula.

In the context of managing open access resources, librarians' information retrieval skills are critical to ensuring accessibility and organization. Temitope (2022) found that the findings indicated a moderate level of information retrieval skills among students, with a significant positive relationship between these skills and the utilization of open access resources ($r = 0.316$, $p < 0.05$). Challenges identified included poor internet connectivity and inadequate browsing skills. The study recommended upgrading internet bandwidth and providing training to enhance information retrieval skills.

Librarians' use of retrieval tools such as catalogues and OPAC reflects their influence on resource organization and access. Umar et al. (2022) found that students effectively applied skills such as using class marks, catalogues, indexes, and OPAC for information retrieval. The study concluded that the high application of these skills positively influenced the management of information resources, recommending continuous training to maintain and enhance these competencies.

Though focused on digital competencies, retrieval skills play a role in identifying and organizing information before archival. Findings indicated that while staff possessed good computer skills, they lacked proficiency in scanning, editing, and archival skills necessary for digitization. The study emphasized the need for comprehensive training programs to equip library staff with the requisite skills for effective management of digital information resources (Emezie and Anunobi, 2019).

Information retrieval skills are an aspect of broader ICT competencies, which affect how well librarians manage library holdings. Ogbomo and Ogbe (2023) findings revealed a significant relationship between ICT skills and preservation efforts, indicating that librarians with higher ICT competencies were more effective in managing information resources. The study recommended ongoing ICT training to enhance librarians' capabilities in preserving and conserving library materials.

Digital resource management in university libraries often hinges on librarians' technical retrieval and organization abilities. A study by Kumar (2024) found that librarians with higher technology skills were more proficient in managing electronic resources, including e-journals, databases, and institutional repositories. The study highlighted the importance of continuous professional development in technology skills to ensure effective management of electronic information resources. Recommendations included regular training and workshops to keep librarians abreast of technological advancements.

The relationship between librarians' digital archiving skills and the management of information resources in university libraries is central to effective digitization and preservation of academic content. A study by Emezie and Anunobi (2019) revealed that while the majority of library staff possessed good computer skills, they lacked proficiency in scanning, editing, document analysis, and archival skills essential for digitization. The study concluded that library staff did not have comprehensive ICT skills required for digitization and recommended training programs to enhance these skills for improved management of digital resources.

Digital archiving skills among librarians influence how well electronic resources are preserved and managed in academic libraries. In a related study, Fayomi et al. (2023) found that digital preservation skills and strategies were significant determinants of electronic information resources management. The study recommended capacity building for library personnel to enhance their digital preservation skills for better management of electronic resources.

Digitization efforts in libraries are often shaped by librarians' practical skills in digital archiving technologies and tools. Adogbeji et al. (2022) showed that dissertations, theses, and staff abstracts were the primary materials digitized, using hardware like desktop computers and scanners, and software such as DSpace and KOHA. The study concluded that factors like availability of digital preservation means, global needs, and funding influenced digitization efforts, and recommended addressing copyright issues and improving funding and power supply to enhance digitization processes.

The effectiveness of managing information resources in university libraries depends on librarians' ICT competencies, including digital archiving capabilities. Ogbomo and Ogbe (2023) found a significant relationship between librarians' ICT skills and their preservation and conservation efforts, indicating that higher ICT competencies led to more effective management of information resources. The authors recommended intensifying preservation and conservation efforts to meet user needs effectively.

Librarians' digital archiving skills play a pivotal role in improving access to information resources in university libraries. Obiozor-Ekeze (2021) highlighted that digitization improves access to information resources but is hindered by challenges such as lack of ICT infrastructure, high cost of equipment, poor funding, and shortage of technical staff. The study recommended providing infrastructural facilities, improved funding, trained manpower, and inclusion of digitization skills in library education to enhance digitization efforts.

Statement of the Problem

In an ideal academic environment, university libraries are expected to function as reliable centers for knowledge access, research support, and information preservation. Librarians are supposed to have up-to-date skills in information retrieval—such as using Boolean search techniques, applying metadata, and navigating electronic databases—as well as the capacity to organize and preserve digital collections effectively. Regular training and professional development are also necessary to keep librarians informed about new tools and methods in library and information management.

Unfortunately, this ideal is far from the reality in many university libraries in North Central Nigeria. Many librarians in these institutions do not have the necessary skills to retrieve digital information efficiently or to manage digital collections properly. There are serious gaps in areas such as metadata usage, digital searching, and database navigation. In addition, most librarians lack proper training in digital archiving, which has led to problems such as data loss, poor organization, and difficulty in accessing stored resources. These technical shortcomings are further worsened by institutional issues, including poor funding, outdated infrastructure, and a lack of support for digital development.

These problems directly affect both the librarians and the users they serve. Students and academic staff often struggle to locate and use digital resources. Librarians, in turn, are unable to provide adequate assistance due to limited skills and tools. The lack of structured archiving methods has made digital collections scattered and difficult to use. As a result, the ability of these libraries to support academic work and contribute meaningfully to research and learning has been seriously weakened.

While there are existing studies that discuss the importance of digital skills in library practice, little attention has been given to the specific situation of university libraries in North Central Nigeria. There is a noticeable gap in research that examines how the information retrieval and archiving skills of librarians affect the way information resources are managed in this region. This study investigated Relationship between librarians' information retrieval skills, digital archiving skills and management of information resources in University libraries in North Central, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between librarians' information retrieval skills and the management of information resources in university libraries in North Central Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between librarians' digital archiving skills, and the management of information resources in university libraries in North Central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between librarians' information retrieval skills and the management of information resources in university libraries in North Central Nigeria
2. There is no significant relationship between librarians' digital archiving skills, and the management of information resources in university libraries in North Central Nigeria

Methodology

A correlational survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised the 254 professional librarians in the six Federal Universities in in North Central Nigeria. For this study, a sample of 254 professional librarians working at the six Federal Universities in North Central Nigeria was used. As a result, since the population

is manageable, there is no sampling for the study. Data was collected by means of structured questionnaire. The first instrument is a structured validated questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Information Retrieval Skills” (QIRS). QIRS is designed to assess the proficiency and competencies of individuals, particularly librarians or information professionals, in retrieving information effectively using various tools, platforms, and techniques. The second questionnaire is titled “Questionnaire on Digital Archiving Skills” (QDAS). QDAS is designed to assess an individual's or an organization's competencies and knowledge related to digital archiving.

The third instrument is a self-structured validated questionnaire on “Management of Information Resources Questionnaire” (MIRQ). It is designed to assess the effectiveness of information resource management within libraries. It is a 12-item questionnaire structured on a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) with nominal values 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. Cronbach’s Alpha was used to check the internal consistency of QIRS, QDAS and MIRQ and their respective reliability values obtained were 0.78, 0.81 and 0.71. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions while linear regression analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level

Results, Interpretation and Discussion of Finding

Table 1: Pearson r on information retrieval skills and management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria (N=254)

Pearson Correlation	r	Remark
Information retrieval and Information resources	0.88	Strong positive relationship

Table 1 shows that there is a strong positive relationship of 0.88 existing between information retrieval skills and management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria

Table 2: Pearson r on digital archiving skills and management of information resources in university libraries (N=254)

Sources of variance	Information resources (r)	Remark
Digital archiving skills and Information resources	0.59	Moderate positive relationship

Table 2 shows that there is a moderate positive relationship of 0.59 existing between digital retrieval skills management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria

Table 3: Linear regression on significant relationship between information retrieval skills and management of information resources in university libraries

R	R ²	Stdized Coefths (β)	df	t	F	Sig.
.387a	.150	.387	252(1)	20.454	44.319	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Information Resources Management
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Information Retrieval Skills

A simple linear regression analysis showed a moderate positive relationship between Information Retrieval Skills and Information Resources Management, with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.387. The model explained 15% of the variance (R² = 0.150) in Information Resources Management, indicating a statistically meaningful result. The standardized beta coefficient (β = 0.387) reflects a moderate effect size, and the high t-value (20.454) and F-statistic (44.319) confirm the model's strength. With a highly significant p-value (0.000), the null hypothesis is rejected and therefore concludes that Information Retrieval Skills significantly predict Information Resources Management, though other influencing factors may still exist.

Table 4: Linear regression on significant relationship between digital archiving skills and management of information resources in university libraries

R	R ²	Stdized Coefths (β)	df	t	F	Sig.
.588a	.345	.588	252(1)	9.504	132.990	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Information Resources Management
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Archival Skills

A simple linear regression analysis was conducted to test the hypothesis which stated that *there is no significance influence of digital archival skills of librarians on their information resources management* indicates a strong and statistically significant relationship between in university libraries. With a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.588 and an R² of 0.345, the model explains 34.5% of the variance in information resource management was explained by the digital archival skills of librarians. The standardized beta coefficient (β = 0.588), along with a significant t-value (9.504) and F-statistic (132.990), further confirms the strength and reliability of this relationship.

These findings imply that enhancing digital archiving skills among library personnel can lead to significant improvements in the management of information resources. University libraries should prioritize training programs and capacity-building initiatives in digital

archiving to strengthen information organization, accessibility, and preservation. Investing in these skills is not only vital for current operational efficiency but also for future-proofing library services in an increasingly digital academic environment.

Discussion of Findings

The finding revealed that there is a strong positive relationship between information retrieval skills and management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. This finding agreed with the finding of Ekenna and Mabawonku (2013) that there is a high positive relationship between librarians' information retrieval skills and the effective management of library resources. Their study indicated that librarians with advanced retrieval skills were better at ensuring that users accessed the right information promptly, thereby optimizing resource utilization. This finding supported that of Umar et al. (2022) that librarians with proficient retrieval skills enhance user satisfaction by providing accurate and timely access to resources. This contributes to effective resource management by ensuring that library services align with user needs.

The corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between information retrieval skills and management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. This finding supported that of Adekannbi (2016) and Temitope (2022) that there is a significant positive relationship between information retrieval competencies and resource management in academic libraries in Nigeria. Their study revealed that librarians with strong retrieval skills could better optimize library systems for resource sharing and collection management.

The finding also revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between digital retrieval skills and management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. This finding means that as librarians improve their digital retrieval skills, the effectiveness of how information resources are managed also tends to improve, but not in a perfectly linear way. This finding agreed with the finding of Temitope (2022) that many librarians possess basic digital retrieval skills but lack advanced competencies, which limits the potential positive impact of these skills on resource management. Obiozor-Ekeze (2021) argued that digital retrieval skills alone are insufficient for effective resource management due to infrastructure challenges, such as inadequate internet access and outdated systems, which hinder their application. On the other hand, this finding opposed that of Ogbomo and Ogbe (2023) who found a strong positive correlation between librarians' digital retrieval skills and their ability to effectively organize and provide access to digital and electronic resources in academic libraries. Skilled

professionals retrieve and manage resources more efficiently, ensuring better service delivery. The reason why both findings differ could be as a result of varying opinions of respondents based on geographical location.

The corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is no significant relationship between digital archiving skills and management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. This finding disagreed with that of Fayomi et al. (2023) who confirmed a significant relationship between digital retrieval skills and the efficient management of institutional repositories, emphasizing their role in curating and accessing digital content. This finding opposed that of Emezie and Anunobi (2019) who reported a significant link between digital retrieval skills and improved accessibility to digital resources, as librarians adept at digital tools provide more effective services to users. The reason why both findings differ could be as a result of varying opinions of respondents based on geographical location.

Conclusion

This study underscores the critical role of information retrieval skills in the effective management of information resources in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria. The findings reveal a strong positive relationship between librarians' retrieval competencies and their ability to optimize resource accessibility, enhance user satisfaction, and improve overall library efficiency. However, while digital retrieval skills moderately contribute to resource management, their impact is constrained by infrastructural challenges and varying levels of digital proficiency among librarians.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. University libraries in North East Nigeria should invest in continuous professional development programs focused on strengthening librarians' retrieval skills to maximize resource utilization and improve user experience.
2. Libraries should implement targeted digital literacy training to equip librarians with advanced digital retrieval and archiving skills, ensuring better management of digital resources.
3. Institutions should upgrade library systems, improve internet access, and adopt modern digital tools to enhance the effectiveness of digital retrieval and archiving practices.

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